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AN ANALYTICAL OVERVIEW OF COPYRIGHT STATUS IN INDIA: CONCERNING TOP ECONOMICS OF THE WORLD

Subhajit Panda

Assistant Librarian,
Central Library, Chandigarh University,
NH-95 Ludhiana-Chandigarh State Highway,
Mohali, Punjab - 140413
Email: subhajit.e9641@cumail.in
ORCID Id: 0000-0002-1578-1159

Prof. Rupak Chakravarty

Department of Library and Information Science
Panjab University, Sector 14,
Chandigarh - 160014
Email: rupak@pu.ac.in
ORCID Id: 0000-0001-5046-1663

Abstract

IPR is one the most formidable dimension which plays a pivotal role in the progress, development, and prosperity in the present highly competitive era leading to a knowledge society. Copyright, as well as Industrial Rights, forms the core of IPR. The purpose of the research is to comprehend the changes occurring in the Indian copyright domain in terms of Copyright applications and registrations. Further, to understand the global standing of India in terms of copyright, related rights, and restrictions with the world's top 15 GDPs (Gross Domestic Product). This paper tried to focus on two distinct research problems. The first was assessing the level of knowledge Indian individuals have on copyright and related rights and its upward trend over a chosen 37-month period. The second one looks at how the Indian IPR sector stands concerning the top economies globally. The present study aims to examine the trends in various parameters regarding copyright applications filed and registrations done including their correlation & normality for the period August 2017 to August 2020. Category 2 of the Global Intellectual Property Center (GIPC) International Index, Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations of the world's top 15 economies (GDPs) was also investigated on a 7-point scale. The monthly reports are downloaded from the Copyright Office of India to evaluate the status of the Copyright application and registration. WPS Spreadsheet is used for cleaning poorly structured data and is ready to perform statistical analysis with the help of JASP statistical software. The top 15 GDPs were examined for copyrights, related rights, and limitations using World Bank statistics and The GIPC International IP Index (8th Edition, 2020). The study findings revealed that, among the copyrightable work, literary and dramatic works obtained the most copyright applications and registrations in 2019 and 2017, respectively. Copyright applications and registrations correlated weakly ($r_p = 0.0634$, $p = 0.730$). In the top 15 economies, the USA and UK ranked highest in GIPC Ranking (score=6.63 each).

Keywords: Intellectual Property Rights, Copyright, Copyright Application, Copyright Registration, Indian Copyright Act, GIPC International IP Index

1. Introduction

Intellectual property (IP) is a category of intangible rights protecting commercially valuable products of the human intellect, whereas Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) is the right a person or

company must use its plans, ideas, or other intangible assets without competition, at least for a specific period (Mathur, 2012). Courts can enforce these rights through lawsuits. The intellectual property encourages innovation, growth, and development without the risk of a competitor misusing or stealing the idea. IPR encompasses patents, trademarks, trade designs, and geographical indications, as well as copyright and related rights (Covers all Literary works, Music, Cinematograph films, Sound recording & Artistic works).

No civilized society can afford to disregard the need to encourage creativity. If a writer, artist, designer, playwright, musician, architect, producer of sound recordings, cinematograph films, and computer software designer's work is secured against piracy and unfair exploitation, it stimulates them to create more and motivates others to create (DPIIT, MCI, GOI, n.d.). Copyright concerns have been at the forefront since the printing press, and they've been more complex for lawmakers and IPR holders since the 1970s and the commercialization of the Internet in the 1990s (Nandini, 2007). Copyright discourse intersects values, policies, and technology in academia. These dimensions can help you comprehend how copyright discourse can serve the academy's goal. Technology provides the infrastructure tools for using and developing intellectual works and copyright enforcement; values constitute the ethical foundation for the institution's intellectual activity; and policies embody institutional aims and directives (Horava, 2011).

The copyright application and registration data of any country demonstrate the people's awareness of copyright law and confirm the successful execution of the Copyright Act (existing) in that country. This article evaluates copyright applications and registrations under India's Copyright Act. As a society's economic and social development is influenced by its IPR policies, implementing copyright law, which is part of IPR, promotes economic growth. Based on the foregoing, a comparison of the copyright status of the world's 15 largest economies has been undertaken.

2. Background Study

Copyright in India is administered by the Copyright Act, of 1957 (Copyright Office, DIPP, MCI, 1957), which took effect in January 1958. In 1983, 1984, 1991, 1994, 1999, and 2012, the act was amended and modified. The Indian Copyright Office is presently situated at Dwarka, New Delhi. Section 78 of the Indian Copyright Act, 1957, outlines the 1958 Copyright Rules. Before the Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012, Copyright Rule 1958 remained intact, however with its enforcement on 21st June 2012, prompted revisions to the rule and new copyright regulations arrived in 2013. (Copyright Office, DIPP, MCI, 2013). Artistic work, cinematograph films, computer programs, literary/dramatic work, musical work, and sound recordings are six types of copyright-protected works. Titles, slogans, and logos may have copyright if they contain enough authorship. Any literary, theatrical, musical, or artistic work published during the author's lifetime has a copyright sixty years after the author's death (Copyright Office, DIPP, MCI, 1957; Section 22, Copyright Act, 1957). For anonymous and pseudonymous works, copyright is granted 60 years after first publication, 60 years after the last author's death, and 60 years after first publication if both authors have died (Copyright Office, DIPP, MCI, 1957; Section 23 & 24, Copyright Act, 1957).

According to Section 51, ICA, 1957 (Copyright Office, DIPP, MCI, 1957), copyright in a work shall be deemed to be infringed if any unauthorized person does anything the owner of the copyright or permits for profit unless he was unaware and had no reasonable grounds to believe such communication to the public would be an infringement of copyright. Section 65A(1) of the Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012 states that anyone who circumvents an effective technological measure applied to protect any of the rights conferred by this Act, to infringe such rights, shall be punished with imprisonment which may extend to two years and shall also be liable to a fine (Badigannavar, 2018). India has a Copyright Enforcement Advisory Council (CEAC) and a Copyright Board to adjudicate

copyright cases. The Copyright Board is a quasi-judicial body consisting of a chairman and two or more, but not more than fourteen, other members for adjudicating specific copyright cases.

Some unauthorized uses of copyright work for certain specific reasons are allowed by law and they are not considered as an infringement of that work and such unauthorized use is termed as “fair use” or “fair dealing” (Ahuja, 2015). In India, provisions regarding Fair use or fair dealing are dealt with in “Exceptions To Infringement Under Copyright Act, 1957”, under Section 52 of the Copyright Act (Copyright Office, DIPP, MCI, 1957) permitting limited use of copyright material without the owner’s authorization. These exceptions are very comprehensive and are beyond the scope of the present study.

3. Literature Review

In social science research, copyright and related rights are a familiar concern, but the topic of the current paper—a survey to analyze the trends of copyright applications and registration over 37 months—has not previously been examined. Another entirely novel approach in this field compares the state of copyrights, related rights, and their limits in the top 15 economies in the world on a recognized 7-point scale.

4. Objectives of the Study

Based on the scope of the study, the following objectives have been undertaken:

- i) To assess the status of Applications and Registrations for various copyright types including Artistic, Cinematograph Film, Computer Software, Literary and Dramatic works, Music, and Sound Recording individually.
- ii) To compare statistically the status of overall copyrights applications and registrations for 37 months.
- iii) To ascertain the correlation between the variables application and registration as the 2 core domains of the Indian Copyright Act (ICA).
- iv) To analyze and compare the status of *Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations* of the world’s top 15 economies on a 7 Point Scale.

5. Designing of Research Questions

Copyright is a fundamental part of IPR, and every country should promote and inspire content creators by protecting them against copyright infringements. With an e-filing system, it would be beneficial to study copyright applications and registration. To fulfill the following aims, the study analyses copyright applications and registration data from August 2017 to August 2020. This study examined copyright filing and registration patterns in India. This study will contribute to scholarly understanding by exploring IPR trends and patterns. The research question of this study is to understand,

- i) What are the changes taking place in the Indian copyright scenario in the IPR era for the period August 2017 to August 2020?
- ii) What is the global standing of India in terms of copyright, related right, and limitations of the same among the world’s top 15 GDPs (Gross Domestic Product)?

6. Research Methodology

In order to analyze the above-said data, the monthly reports available on the Copyright Office of India (available at <http://copyright.gov.in/>) pertaining to both copyright applications and registrations (copyright.gov.in, n.d.) were downloaded belonging to the period of study selected. As these reports were in PDF format, which is not amenable to data processing, each file was individually converted into .xlsx and .csv format. To accomplish this, the authors used the services of a popular pdf-handling portal, Ilovepdf (<https://www.ilovepdf.com/>). After the successful conversion, several distortions were

noted leading to nonconformity to statistical software. To address the improperly formatted data, data cleaning was undertaken to rectify any errors and increase reliability and accuracy. Post data cleansing, it was processed by WPS Spreadsheet and JASP statistical s/w package (an open-source statistics program). To analyze the status of the world's top 15 GDPs pertaining to "Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations", relevant data were extracted from the GIPC International IP Index (8th Edition, 2020) on a 7-point scale. To identify the global top 15 economies (2019), the World Bank statistical database was consulted (Worldbank.org, 2019).

7. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the total copyright applications filed from August 2017 to August 2020 (37 months) and table 2 shows the registrations. Due to data availability, the average monthly applications and registrations for 2017 & 2020 are only calculated for five (August-December) & eight (January-August) months. Note that successful registrations for any given year may include applications filed the previous year. In 2016, the copyright office received 317 monthly applications, compared to 695.2 average monthly registrations of artistic works. All the following graphics include a trendline (or line of best fit), and a straight or curved line in a chart that shows the general pattern or overall direction of the data. Moving averages smooth out data volatility to reveal patterns and trends.

Table 1: Copyright Applications (August 2017 - August 2020)

Works	2017	2018	2019	2020	Sum	Avg monthly
Artistic	1585	5030	5781	2425	14821	400.57
Cinematograph Film	118	351	345	248	1062	28.70
Computer Software	602	2298	1681	984	5565	150.41
Literary/ Dramatic	3966	10561	11895	8093	34515	932.84
Music	133	300	320	215	968	26.16
Sound Recording	1408	882	1125	448	3863	104.41
Total Applications	7812	19422	21147	12413	60794	
Avg. monthly	1562.40	1618.50	1762.25	1551.63		

Table 2: Copyright Registrations (August 2017 - August 2020)

Works	2017	2018	2019	2020	Sum	Avg monthly
Artistic	3476	5230	4565	2026	15297	413.43
Cinematograph Film	89	340	270	78	777	21.00
Computer Software	633	2147	1062	538	4380	118.38
Literary/ Dramatic	4135	8185	8408	5995	26723	722.24
Music	29	66	52	28	175	4.73
Sound Recording	1018	736	708	374	2836	76.65
Total Registrations	9380	16704	15065	9039	50188	
Avg. monthly	1876	1392	1255.42	1129.88		

7. 1. Artistic Works

Copyright shall subsist in any original artistic work comprising of paintings, sculptures, graphics, cartoons, etchings, lithographs, photography, drawings (including a diagram, map, chart, or plan), buildings, models of buildings, molds, and casts for sculptures. Figure 1 shows the status of applications received (average monthly) by the Indian Copyright Office for the registration of various artistic works and approved registrations.

Figure 1: Average Monthly Copyright Application vs Registration of Artistic Works

Figure 1 reflects a rise in the average monthly copyright applications for artistic works from 2017 (317) to 2019 (481.75, maximum). In 2018 and 2020, 419.16 and 303.13 average monthly applications were accepted. Average monthly registrations in the artistic works domain are falling from 2017 to 2020 with 695.2, 435.83, 380.42, and 253.25 monthly average registrations, respectively. The moving average trendline confirms these findings.

7.2. Cinematograph Film

Under the ICA 1957, copyright of Cinematograph Film has a significant place from its beginning. Cinematograph film is any series of visual pictures recorded on any material (translucent or not) that may be seen as a moving picture or recorded on another material (translucent or not) that can show it. This includes VHS. Figure 2 depicts the average monthly applications received by the Indian Copyright Office for the registration of cinematograph films and the successful registrations after approval.

Figure 2: Average Monthly Copyright Application vs Registration of Cinematograph Film

Figure 2 displays the average monthly copyright applications for cinematograph films from 2017 (23.6) to 2020 (31.00, maximum). In 2018 & 2019, 29.25 & 28.75 cinematograph film applications were accepted per month. The average monthly registrations of cinematograph films climb sharply in 2018 from 2017 and diminish in 2019 and 2020. The figure was 17.8, 28.34, 22.5, and 9.75 from 2017 to 2020 respectively. The moving average trendline also corroborates with the above findings.

7.3. Computer Software

Software and programs are computer instructions. Copyright Law covers computer software IPR in India. ICA defines a “Computer program” as a set of instructions represented in words, codes, algorithms, or any other form, including a machine-readable medium, that causes a computer to complete a task or achieve a result. It’s a self-contained program that performs specified functions. Figure 3 shows the average monthly applications received by the Indian Copyright Office for the registration of various computer software and the successful registrations after approval.

Figure 3: Average Monthly Copyright Application vs Registration of Computer Software

Figure 3 reflects the average monthly software copyright applications from 2017 to 2020, with the most in 2018 (avg. monthly=191.5). In 2017, the average number of monthly software applications was 120.4, which rose sharply in 2018 and then fell in 2019 and 2020 to 140.08 and 123.00. Figure 3 shows a similar pattern for average monthly software registrations. The average monthly registrations maximum for 2018 (was 178.92), and the rest were 126.6, 88.5, and 67.25 for 2017, 2019, and 2020, respectively. The moving average trendline verifies the above findings.

7.4. Literary/Dramatic Work

Computer programs are protected as “literary works” in India. Dramatic work comprises any recitation, choreography, or dumb performance with a defined scenic arrangement or acting form, but not a film. Figure 4 represents the average monthly applications received by the Indian Copyright Office for the registration of Literary/Dramatic works and the successful registrations after approval.

Figure 4: Average Monthly Copyright Application vs Registration of Literary/Dramatic Works

Figure 4 displays an increase in average monthly copyright applications for literary/dramatic works from 2017 to 2020. In 2020, the average monthly copyright applications for literary/dramatic works was maximum (1011.63), followed by 2017, 2018, and 2019 with 793.2, 880.08, and 991.25 respectively. In the case of literary/dramatic work average monthly copyright registrations, the trendline drops from 2017 to 2018 and then climbs in 2019 & 2020, with the most registrations in 2017 (827) and for the remaining years 682.08, 700.67, and 749.38. The moving average trendline ensures the above findings.

7.5. Musical Works

ICA, 1957 protects musical works that feature graphical notation, but no words or actions meant to be sung, spoken, or performed with music. The creator or author owns the copyright in musical works, but this can vary based on employment or licensing arrangements. Figure 5 shows the average monthly applications received by the Indian Copyright Office for the registration of musical works and the approved registrations.

Figure 5: Average Monthly Copyright Application vs Registration of Musical Works

Figure 5 shows the average monthly copyright applications for musical works from 2017 (26.6) to 2020 (26.88, maximum). In 2018 & 2019, monthly musical work applications were 25 & 26.67. The average monthly number of musical work registrations is decreasing continuously from 2017 (5.8) to 2020 (4.34). It was 5.5 and 4.34 in 2018 and 2019 respectively. Figure 5 shows a gap between the registration and application graphs. The moving average trendline confirms the above findings.

7.6. Sound Recording

Only ICA-compliant sound recordings have copyright. If copyright was broken or infringed in the making of a literary, dramatic, or musical sound recording, it will not exist in the sound recording. Sound recordings and their subjects have separate copyrights. A recording’s producer is its creator. Figure 6 depicts the status of applications received (average monthly) by the Indian Copyright Office for the registration of various sound recordings and approved registrations.

Figure 6: Average Monthly Copyright Application vs Registration of Sound Recording

Figure 6 illustrates the average monthly copyright applications for sound recordings from 2017 to 2020, with the maximum average monthly applications received in 2017 (281.6). In 2018 and 2019, monthly sound recording applications were 73.5 and 93.75. In 2017, the average monthly sound recording registration (203.6) was the maximum. And, between 2018-2020 the average monthly registration was 61.34, 59, and 46.75, correspondingly. Figure 6 shows that 2017 saw a sharp spike in both applications and registered sound recordings. The moving average trendline confirms the above findings.

7.7. Overall Copyright Applications Status (type based)

Figure 7(a & b): Sum and Average Monthly Copyright Applications Status

From figure 7(a), literary and dramatic works had the most copyright applicants (34515), followed by artistic (14821), computer software (5565), and sound recordings (3863). Cinematography film had more applications (1062) than music (968). During the study period (August 2017 - August 2020), 60794 copyright applications were filed for artistic, cinematograph film, computer software (including mobile apps and websites), literary and dramatic, music, and sound recordings. Figure 7(b) illustrates the average monthly approval and registration requests from August 2017 to August 2020. Creative (463.16), cinematograph film (33.19), computer software (including mobile apps and websites), literary and dramatic (1078.59), music (30.25), and sound recordings (120.72) average the same. Literary and dramatic works received the most submissions owing to copyright infringement. Although copyright violations are routinely reported in India, copyright applications are minimal.

7.8. Overall Copyright Registrations Status (type based)

Figure 8(a & b): Sum and Average Monthly Copyright Registrations Status

From figure 8(a), it is evident that literary and dramatic works (26723) had the most distinct & individual registrations, followed by artistic (15297), computer software (4380), and sound recordings (2836). Musical works had the fewest registrations (175), whereas film had more (777). In the study period (August 2017-August 2020), 50188 registrations were made for artistic, cinematograph film, computer software (including mobile apps and websites), literary and dramatic, music, and sound recordings. Figure 8(b) shows the average monthly registrations received by the Indian Copyright Office from August 2017 to August 2020. Artistic (413.43), cinematograph film (21.00), computer software (including mobile apps and websites) (118.38), literary and dramatic (722.24), music (4.73) and sound recordings (76.65) follow a similar pattern. Maximum registrations under literary and dramatic works can be linked to a bigger number of works created and more knowledge of copyright protection due to more violations, thus the number of copyright applications is likewise high. In India, copyright infringements are routinely publicized in the media (e.g. film or music), but registrations are minimal.

7.9. Overall Monthly Average Applications and Registrations Status (year-wise)

Figure 9: Average Monthly Applications and Registrations (comparative chart)

Figure 9 depicts the average monthly copyright applications and registrations in India from August 2017 to August 2020. The plot confirms the common notion that due to increased copyright awareness and because the copyright office now permits the e-Filing of copyright applications online, there would be an upswing in copyright applications, which is a positive trend in the worldwide IPR regime. The year 2019 had the most average monthly copyright applications (1762.25), followed by 2017, 2018, and 2020 with 1562.40, 1618.50, and 1551.63. Whereas, in 2017, the average monthly copyright registrations were 1876, followed by 1392, 1255.42, and 1129.88 in 2018, 2019, and 2020.

These two plots support the general assumption that though the filing of applications regarding copyright registration increased with time (with a deep decrease in 2020) but actual registrations decreased constantly during these 4 years. The reason for this may be a lack of unique works and an increase in the rate of duplication, remixing, and reuse of material due to the increase of open access and internet-based information dissemination tends to more availability of information irrespective of their quality.

8. Statistical Analysis

In our present study, taking the dataset of Total Applications received in each month and Total Registrations of copyright in various fields, two statistical analyses are done to examine mainly the normality distribution and correlation among the variables.

8.1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics is the branch of statistics that develops where necessary, methods for collecting, processing, and quantitative and qualitative analysis of data. The objective of descriptive statistics is to summarize or represent, through statistics, the data available when they are numerous.

There are various types of statistics that are used to describe data:

- Measures of central tendency (i.e., Mean, Median, Mode & Sum)
- Measures of dispersion (i.e., Std. Error of Mean, Std. Deviation, Minimum & Maximum)
- Quartile values (i.e., Valid & Missing values)
- Measures of distribution (i.e., Shapiro-Wilk test for Normality)
- Distribution plots (i.e., Box plot & Q-Q plot)

Table - 3: Descriptive Statistics

		Applications	Registrations
Valid		37	37
Missing		0	0
Mean		1643.081	1356.432
Std. Error of Mean		48.457	70.499
Median		1652.000	1300.000
Mode	*	1510.000	540.000
Std. Deviation		294.755	428.826
Minimum		591.000	540.000
Maximum		2107.000	2514.000
Sum		60794.000	50188.000
		* More than one mode exists, only the first is reported	

8.1.1. Normality Test

Shapiro-Wilk tests were conducted to determine whether the distributions of Applications and Registrations were significantly different from a normal distribution. The Shapiro-Wilk test is the most powerful test to tell if the random sample comes from a normal distribution. The null hypothesis for this test is that the data are normally distributed. The Prob < W value listed in the output is the p-value. If the chosen alpha level is 0.05 (i.e., critical value, $Q = 0.05$) and,

- i) the p -value is less than 0.05, then the null hypothesis that the data are normally distributed is rejected (do not assume a normal distribution).
- ii) the p -value is greater than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is not rejected (assume a normal distribution)

- **Shapiro-Wilk Test**

Table - 4: Shapiro-Wilk Test Result

Variable	W	p^*
Applications	0.907	0.376
Registrations	0.964	0.592

*Critical value ($Q = 0.05$)

Shapiro-Wilk tests were conducted to determine whether the distributions of Applications and Registrations were significantly different from a normal distribution. The following variables had distributions that did not significantly differ from normality based on an alpha of 0.05: Applications ($W = 0.907$, $p = 0.376$) and Registrations ($W = 0.964$, $p = 0.592$). The results are presented in table 4.

8.1.2. Distribution Plots

The Distribution plot splits data into frequency bins and overlays the distribution curve. In the present study, Boxplots (figure 10(a & b)) result in an essentially symmetrical curve, suggesting the data is about normally distributed. The second distribution plot, Q-Q Plots (figure 11(a & b)), exhibits positively skewed and linearly distributed data.

• **Boxplots:**

Figure 10(a & b): Boxplots of Copyright Applications and Registrations

• **Q-Q Plots:**

Figure 11(a & b): Q-Q Plots of Copyright Applications and Registrations

8.2. Correlation Test

A correlation expresses the strength of linkage or co-occurrence between two variables. The most common measure of correlation in statistics is the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) which shows the linear relationship between two sets of data. The correlation coefficient between two continuous-level variables is called Pearson’s *r* or Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient which is represented typically as the letter ‘*r*’ and has a single value between -1 and +1. This value measures the strength of the linkage. (Laerd Statistics, 2020)

8.2.1. Result Details & Calculation:

Table 5: Correlation Test Result & Calculation

<p>X Values</p> <p>$\Sigma = 52608$</p> <p>Mean = 1644</p> <p>$\Sigma (X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1447168$</p> <p>Y Values</p> <p>$\Sigma = 45019$</p> <p>Mean = 1406.844</p> <p>$\Sigma (Y - My)^2 = SSy = 5694568.219$</p> <p>X and Y Combined</p> <p>N = 32</p> <p>$\Sigma (X - Mx)(Y - My) = 181964$</p> <p>R Calculation</p> <p>$r = \Sigma ((X - Mx)(Y - My)) / \sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}$</p> <p>$r = 181964 / \sqrt{((1447168)(5694568.219))}$</p> <p>= 0.0634</p> <p>Meta Numerics (cross-check)</p> <p>r = 0.0634</p>	<p>Key</p> <p>X: X Values</p> <p>Y: Y Values</p> <p>Mx: Mean of X Values</p> <p>My: Mean of Y Values</p> <p>X - Mx & Y - My: Deviation scores</p> <p>(X - Mx)² & (Y - My)²: Deviation Squared</p> <p>(X - Mx) (Y - My): Product of Deviation Scores</p>
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8.2.2. Pearson Correlations Matrix

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	Pearson's r	p	VS- MPR ⁺	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI
Applications - Registrations	0.0634	0.730	1.000	-0.292	0.403
* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001					
z Vovk-Sellke Maximum p -Ratio: Based on the p-value, the maximum possible odds in favour of H ₀ over H ₁ equals 1/(-e p log(p)) for p d” .37 (Sellke, Bayarri, & Berger, 2001).					

A positive correlation was observed between Applications and Registrations ($r_p = 0.0634, p = 0.730$). The correlation coefficient between Applications and Registrations was 0.0634 ($p = <0.05$), indicating a weak effect between the two variables (nb. the nearer the value is to zero, the weaker the relationship). This correlation indicates that as Applications rise, so do Registrations. Table 5 shows the brief calculation and table 6 displays the relationships.

8.2.3. Correlation Plot

Figure 12: Correlation Plots of Copyright Applications and Registrations

Pearson correlation requires linearity between variables. Curvature in any scatterplot pair violates this notion. Figure 12 shows a scatterplot and correlation histogram. This result indicates a weak linear correlation between the applications and registration variables.

9. The Global Innovation Policy Center (GIPC) Ranking of Top 15 GDP:

Table - 7: GIPC Category 2 Performance of the World’s Top 15 Economics

GDP Rank	Country	GIPC Category 2: Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations (7-Point Scale)							Total
		I-9	I-10	I-11	I-12	I-13	I-14	I-15	
1	US	0.63	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	6.63
2	China	0.53	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.25	0.25	0.50	2.53
3	Japan	0.53	1.00	0.50	0.50	0.75	0.75	1.00	5.03
4	Germany	0.63	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	6.38
5	UK	0.63	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	6.63
6	France	0.74	0.75	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75	5.99
7	India	0.47	0.25	0.75	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.25	2.22
8	Italy	0.66	0.50	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.50	0.75	4.66

9	Brazil	0.63	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.25	0.25	1.88
10	Canada	0.63	0.50	0.25	0.25	0.25	1.00	1.00	3.88
11	Russia	0.74	0.50	0.75	0.50	0.00	0.25	0.00	2.74
12	South Korea	0.74	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.50	5.99
13	Australia	0.63	1.00	1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.75	5.88
14	Spain	0.63	0.50	0.75	0.50	0.75	0.75	0.50	4.38
15	Mexico	0.79	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.50	0.25	0.75	2.79
	Total	9.61	10	10.25	8.5	9	10.25	10	

9.1. Category 2: Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations

Table 7 summarizes the GIPC International IP Index Indicators pertaining to “*Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations*” reflecting its contribution to the strength of an economy’s environment. The category consists of 7 Indicators (I-9 to I-15) and their score out of 7 (max). These indicators highlight the challenging environment for content creators and copyright holders in most sampled economies (53 global economies). Indicator 9 (I-9) deals with the Copyright (and related rights) term of protection wherein Mexico attained the maximum score of 0.79 closely followed by France, Russia, and South Korea, each scoring 0.74. Countries need to apply laws to prevent, deter, and remedy online infringement of copyright and related rights. Indicator 10 (I-10) deals with the Legal measures that provide necessary exclusive rights that prevent infringement of copyrights and related rights (including Web hosting, streaming, and linking). Under this parameter 6 of the top economies of the world have done well scoring 1, which is the maximum. Indicator 11 (I-11) addresses expeditious injunctive-style relief and disabling of infringing content online (New addition indicator in 2018). China and Brazil scored 0 in this indicator.

Figure 13 (a & b): GIPC Category 2 Performance of World’s Top 15 Economies

I-12 focuses on the availability of frameworks that promote cooperative action against online piracy and clear standards for the limitation of liability for copyright and related rights infringement by Internet service providers (ISPs) that expeditiously remove infringing material upon obtaining knowledge of it through promoting cooperation between them and rights holders to address online piracy, and respects and protects users’ rights. Brazil and Mexico scored 0 in this indicator. I-13 measures the Scope of limitations and exceptions to copyrights and related rights as per the Berne three-step test wherein India and Russia have performed poorly while I-14 evaluates digital rights management (DRM) legislation. Countries with primary and/ or secondary legislation relating to DRM and technological

protection measures score high in this indicator. The last indicator in this category, I-15 revolves around the clear implementation of policies and guidelines requiring that any proprietary software used on government ICT systems should be licensed software. In all these 7 indicators (I-9 to I-15), the world’s top 15 economies (GDP rank 1 to 15) have scored between 0-1, 1 being the maximum. The top 15 economies have relatively performed well in I-11 and I-14 (score = 10.25) while the lowest score was reported for I-12 (score = 8.5). Again, the United States of America (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK) have obtained the overall highest rank pertaining to copyright with each scoring 6.63 closely followed by Germany (6.38) while Brazil (1.88), India (2.22) and China (2.53) occupied the bottom three positions in this category.

Figure 14: Relative Chart of Copyright Performance of the World’s Top 15 Economies

Figure 14 above reveals that having higher GDP does not bear a correlation with a higher rank in Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations. This is true for most of the top 15 GDPs reflecting upon the urgent need to amend, amplify, improve, and implement copyright policies and laws for sustainable copyright practices and to motivate content creators.

10. Conclusion

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), a global forum for intellectual property services, policy, information, and cooperation enforced three major initiatives directly linked to copyright protection viz. The Berne Convention (1886), the WIPO Copyright Treaty (WCT) (1996), and the WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty (WPPT) (1996). But the issues & challenges faced in protecting IPR have undergone a major transformation in the fast-paced economic, social, cultural, and technological development (Dayananda Murthy, 2017). Besides technological development & digitization, unethical use of fair use principles sometimes also causes serious issues in copyright protection (US Copyright, n.d.). In India, copyright registration is not necessary as the registration is considered only for recording purposes and it neither creates/confers any new right nor a prerequisite for initiating action against infringement (Dalmia). But the application filed for copyright registration indicates the degree of awareness amongst stakeholders, enforcement agencies, professional users like the scientific and academic communities, and members of the public on various issues relating to copyright and related rights.

The average monthly copyright applications received climbed from 2017 to 2019 and peaked in 2019 (1762.25), before declining in 2020. Maximum monthly average copyright registrations were in 2017 (1876.00), then fall from 2018 to 2020. These results support the general assumption that due to increased copyright awareness and the fact that the copyright office now facilitates the e-Filing of

copyright applications online, the rate of copyright applications increases with time, except in 2020 due to the uncertain outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The lower rate of copyright registration may be owing to a lack of unique works and an increase in duplication, remix, and reuse due to open access and internet-based information distribution. The yearly copyright application & registration plot does not follow the same trend, but a weak positive correlation was discovered ($r_p = 0.0634$, $p = 0.730$).

Along with changing technology and market dynamics, IPR is also powerfully influenced by Indian relations with the world economy (Booth, 2015). While examining the top 15 economies with GIPC Ranking indicators of Category 2 (i.e., Copyrights, Related Rights, and Limitations), it was found that the United States of America (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK) achieved the overall highest rank pertaining to copyright with each scoring 6.63 closely followed by Germany (6.38) while Brazil (1.88), India (2.22) and China (2.53) occupied the bottom three positions in this category. In this aspect, Prof. Ian Hargreaves suggested that the UK & USA should resolutely pursue their international interests in IP, particularly concerning emerging economies such as China and India, based upon positions grounded in economic evidence (Hargreaves, 2011). Effective protection and enforcement of copyright and related rights play an important role in helping stimulate this activity. Economies with stronger copyright protection and enforcement have higher levels of creative output leading to the possibility of a better tomorrow.

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